

DETERMINATION OF ORDER EXECUTION PRIORITY USING A FUZZY DECISION SYSTEM. THE CASE OF PRODUCTS OBTAINED BY INJECTION MOLDING OF PLASTIC

Andrei-Mihai PRADA ¹, Gabriel PRADA ², Mihai TĂMĂȘAN ³, Florin BLAGA ⁴, Lajos VERES ⁵
PhD Student ^{1,5}, PG Student ^{2,3}, Prof. PhD ⁴
University of Oradea
Oradea, Universității Str., No. 1, Romania
andrei.prada.97@gmail.com¹, prada_gabriel99@yahoo.com²,
mihaitamasan20092000@gmail.com³, fblaga@uoradea.ro⁴, ocsike74@yahoo.com⁵
<https://www.uoradea.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – *This paper aims to present the development and implementation of a fuzzy logic system used for production scheduling, designed to improve the decision-making processes and manage uncertainties.*

Methodology/approach – *The research adopts a methodological framework that combines principles of fuzzy logic with production scheduling theories. A system was developed and tested using real data from production. The approach involved creating a set of rules, tailored to meet specific needs in the production environment.*

Findings – *The system improves the efficiency of production scheduling through dynamic adjustment of priorities based on input variables. This helps to adhere to deadlines and improves resource management.*

Research limitations/implications – *The study is limited because it approaches specific production scenarios and requires adjustment for use in other industrial contexts. Future research could improve the model by introducing other variables to make it more versatile.*

Practical implications – *The system can improve production efficiency and assure adherence to deadlines, providing a useful tool for production managers.*

Originality/value – *The study highlights the advantages fuzzy logic offer when it comes to managing the uncertainties in production processes and it provides a framework that can be adapted and extended for broader use in production operations.*

Key words: *fuzzy logic, production scheduling, decisional system.*

Introduction

Production scheduling represents a fundamental pillar of operational management, having a direct impact on a company's efficiency and competitiveness. In a more and more dynamic industrial environment, the ability to optimally organize and plan production activities becomes essential on the long term. This complex process involves not only efficient resource management and production schedules, but also a very tight bond between the various departments of a company. The main objective of production scheduling is to assure a continuous and optimized flow of operations, while minimizing costs and avoid wasting resources. In the ever-evolving landscape of manufacturing and production, the necessity for precision and adaptability in scheduling processes becomes crucial. Traditional scheduling techniques, although efficient in certain scenarios, often meet difficulties trying to face the

uncertainty and complexity of the modern industry. As the companies struggle to obtain increased efficiency, reduced costs and a better resource usage, emergent technologies are researched to revolutionize the existing production scheduling methodologies. One of these technologies that gained popularity in recent years is fuzzy logic. Introducing a certain degree of flexibility and adaptability in programming algorithms, fuzzy logic systems have the potential to overcome the dynamic nature of manufacturing environment.

For example, Tedford and Lowe (2003) highlight the importance of fuzzy logic when it comes to considering multiple criteria and making fast decisions during production, showing how fast it can adapt to changes in the dynamic field of production. Moreover, Klir and Yuan (1995) provide a comprehensive theoretical foundation for fuzzy logic, emphasizing its application in systems where uncertainty and vagueness are prevalent. Their work underscores the importance of fuzzy sets in modelling complex production processes.

In his paper, Benhamian (2016) presents a series of scheduling procedures based on fuzzy sets for different types of production: single machine, parallel machines, flow shop, job shop and open shop.

This paper explores the application of fuzzy logic in production scheduling, bringing into light the principles and advantages of its implementation in the industrial setting.

The development of a production scheduling system based on fuzzy sets

Production scheduling is an essential process when it comes to managing the required operations, which involves the organization and planning of the manufacturing activities so that the efficiency is maximized, costs are minimized and unpleasant situations such as missing a deadline are avoided. Production planning involves making decisions based on the analysis of a complex set of data, such as demand estimation, production capacity evaluation, required resources allocation, operation programming, production monitoring, stock management, etc. Based on the complexity of the data, making a decision can sometimes be very difficult. Therefore, managers rely on well-established rules and standards and, with the advancement of technology, on certain specialized software. However, Jain and Meeran (1999) review deterministic job-shop scheduling, highlighting the limitations of traditional methods and proposing innovative solutions to overcome these challenges. Their work demonstrates that fuzzy logic can effectively adapt to real-time changes in production conditions, improving overall scheduling efficiency and responsiveness. The integration of fuzzy logic helps in navigating the vast solution space, ensuring optimal scheduling outcomes even in complex and dynamic environments. Moreover, Negnevitsky (2005) research mentions the versatility of fuzzy logic systems in different industrial applications, including production and quality management. Even so, if the resources are limited, certain problems can appear when it comes to production management.

One such problem could arise when, for example, multiple orders require the use of the same machine (equipment). Resolving such a problem is the subject of this paper, which aims to develop a decisional system based on fuzzy sets, to help establish the priority of each of the orders. The system was developed using the fuzzy toolbox in Matlab. The priority will be determined based on three criteria: production time (PT), due date (DD) by which the products must be delivered, and the existing safety stock (SS). The block diagram of the decisional system is provided in figure 1. Therefore, these three criteria will represent the three input variables and the output variable will be the priority (P), together constituting the linguistic variables of the system.

Figure 1. The block diagram of the decisional system

The influence the input variables have on the priority is as it follows:

- Production time (PT) is defined by the number of hours required to finish manufacturing of an order. It is directly proportional to the priority, meaning that orders with longer production times will take precedence over smaller batches.
- Due date (DD) is defined as the time when the product must be delivered. It is inversely proportional to the priority, therefore orders with a closer deadline will be prioritized.
- Safety stock (SS) is defined as the number of units of the product to be manufactured, that are currently in stock. The safety stock is inversely proportional to the priority, therefore precedence will be given to the products with lower safety stock.

Going forward, the range of values for the input and output variables will be determined. These are as follows:

The domain of values for the production time PT is presented in formula (1).

$$PT: D_{PT} = [0, 120] \text{ [hours]} \quad (1)$$

The domain of values for the due date (DD) is presented in formula (2).

$$DD: D_{DD} = [0, 12] \text{ [days]} \quad (2)$$

The domain of values for the safety stock SS is presented in formula (3).

$$SS: D_{SS} = [0, 200] \text{ [%]} \quad (3)$$

The domain of values for the priority P is presented in formula (4).

$$P: D_P = [0, 10] \quad (4)$$

After that, the linguistic terms associated with each variable and the corresponding membership function for each linguistic term will be determined.

The linguistic degrees associated with PT are established in formula (5).

$$PT: LT_{PT} = \{VS, S, M, L, VL\} \quad (5)$$

Where: VS – very short, S – short, M – medium, L – large, VL – very large.

The linguistic degrees associated DD are established in formula (6).

$$DD: LT_{DD} = \{VC, C, M, F, VF\} \quad (6)$$

Where: VC – very close, C – close, M – medium, F – far, VF – very far.

The linguistic degrees associated with SS are established in formula (7).

$$SS: LT_{SS} = \{VS, S, M, B, VB\} \quad (7)$$

Where: VS – very small, S – small, M – medium, B – big, VB – very big.

The linguistic degrees associated with P are established in formula (8).

$$P: LT_P = \{NP, LP, MP, HP, VHP\} \quad (8)$$

Where: NP – non-priority, LP – low priority, MP – Medium Priority, HP – high priority, VHP – very high priority.

The membership functions of the input variables are presented in figure 2 and for the output variable, the priority, the functions are illustrated in figure 3.

The next step involves establishing the decisional inferences and the rule base. The rule base is a set of instructions that establish the influence the input variables have upon the output variable. Because there are five input variables, each of them having five membership functions, the total number of rules will be 125. Below there are some examples of rules:

1. If (PT is VS) and (DD is VC) and (SS is VS) then (P is HP)
2. If (PT is VS) and (DD is VC) and (SS is S) then (P is MP)
3. If (PT is VS) and (DD is VC) and (SS is M) then (P is MP)
4. If (PT is VS) and (DD is VC) and (SS is B) then (P is MP)
5. If (PT is VS) and (DD is VC) and (SS is VB) then (P is LP)
6. If (PT is VS) and (DD is C) and (SS is VS) then (P is MP)
7. If (PT is VS) and (DD is C) and (SS is S) then (P is MP)

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53. If (PT is M) and (DD is VC) and (SS is M) then (P is HP)
 54. If (PT is M) and (DD is VC) and (SS is B) then (P is MP)
 55. If (PT is M) and (DD is VC) and (SS is VB) then (P is MP)
 56. If (PT is M) and (DD is C) and (SS is VS) then (P is HP)
 57. If (PT is M) and (DD is C) and (SS is S) then (P is HP)
 58. If (PT is M) and (DD is C) and (SS is M) then (P is MP)
 59. If (PT is M) and (DD is C) and (SS is B) then (P is MP)
 60. If (PT is M) and (DD is C) and (SS is VB) then (P is MP)
 61. If (PT is M) and (DD is M) and (SS is VS) then (P is HP)

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119. If (PT is VL) and (DD is F) and (SS is B) then (P is MP)
 120. If (PT is VL) and (DD is F) and (SS is VB) then (P is MP)
 121. If (PT is VL) and (DD is VF) and (SS is VS) then (P is HP)
 122. If (PT is VL) and (DD is VF) and (SS is S) then (P is MP)
 123. If (PT is VL) and (DD is VF) and (SS is M) then (P is MP)
 124. If (PT is VL) and (DD is VF) and (SS is B) then (P is MP)
 125. If (PT is VL) and (DD is VF) and (SS is VB) then (P is LP)

Figure 2. Membership functions associated to the input variables

Figure 3. Membership function corresponding to the output variable

The final step is the data defuzzification, which means transforming the output variable from fuzzy values into concrete values that can be used and applied in production activities. Essentially, the fuzzy results are converted into real decisions or actions. The method used for defuzzification will be the centre of gravity method, as it is one of the most commonly used methods in practice. The decisional system that was developed is illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 5 presents the variation surface of the output variable (P) in relation to the input variables DD and PT.

Figure 4. The decisional system developed in the fuzzy logic toolbox in Matlab

Figure 5. The variation surface of the output variable P in relation to the input variables DD and PT

Case study

To validate the functionality of the developed system, a case study will be examined. Three molds need to run in series production on an injection molding machine. Moreover, besides the series production, there is another mold for which a trial must be held, in order to send parts to the client so that the mold can be validated. The input data associated with each mold are as follows:

- For the 1st mold:

- Production time PT: a series of 120 000 parts must be manufactured, with a standard time of 1.50 seconds per part. The mold has 8 cavities, so the cycle time is 12 seconds, resulting in a production rate of 40 parts/minute. Therefore, the time required to finish the whole batch is 50 hours;
- Due date DD: 7 days;
- Safety stock SS: 50% of a batch (60 000 pcs);

- For the 2nd mold:

- Production time PT: a series of 18 000 parts must be manufactured, with a standard time of 12 seconds per part. The mold has 2 cavities, so the cycle time is 24 seconds, resulting in a production rate of 5 parts/minute. Therefore, the time required to finish the whole batch is 60 hours;
- Due date DD: 5 days;
- Safety stock SS: 100% of a batch (18 000 pcs);

- For the 3rd mold:

- Production time PT: a series of 36 000 parts must be manufactured, with a standard time of 11 seconds. The mold has 2 cavities, so the cycle time is 22 seconds, resulting in a production rate of 5.45 parts/minute. Therefore, the time required to finish the whole batch is 110 hours;
- Due date DD: 8 days;
- Safety stock SS: 50% of a whole batch (18 000 pcs);

- For the 4th mold:

- Production time PT: a series of 100 parts must be manufactured, with a standard time of 36 seconds. The mold has 1 cavity, so the cycle time is 36 seconds, resulting in a production rate of 1.67 parts/minute. Therefore, the time required to finish the whole batch is 1 hour;
- Due date DD: 1 day;
- Safety stock SS: 0% of a whole batch (0 pcs);

The input data for each mold will be successively introduced in the decisional system which will automatically determine, based on the decisional inferences, the priority associated with each mold. Figure 6 exemplifies the way the system works, determining the priority of the 1st mold. Similarly, the process is repeated for the other three molds, resulting in the following priorities:

- Priority P for the 1st mold: 5.83.
- Priority P for the 2nd mold: 5.
- Priority P for the 3rd mold: 6.67.
- Priority P for the 4th mold: 6.67.

Therefore, the molds with the biggest priority are the 3rd and the 4th. A very important tie-breaking criterion could be the due date. If the 3rd mold is prioritized, then the due date of the 4th mold would be exceeded. Logically, the 4th mold should take precedence. Table 1 presents the input and output data obtained using the decisional system.

Figure 6. The priority of the 1st mold determined with the centre of gravity method

Table 1. Input and output data resulted from the case study

Mold	Production time PT [hours]	Due date DD [days]	Safety stock [%]	Priority
1	50	7	50	5.83
2	60	5	100	5
3	110	8	50	6.67
4	1	1	0	6.67

Conclusions

The results determined in this paper demonstrate that the application of fuzzy logic in production scheduling emerges as a promising direction for improving efficiency, adaptability and the overall performance in manufacturing processes. The inherent capability of fuzzy logic to adapt to uncertainties and imprecisions perfectly aligns with the dynamic nature of the modern industry. By introducing flexible decision-making framework, fuzzy logic allows production schedules to become more responsive to real-world variations, reducing disruptions and optimizing the management of resources. The capability of fuzzy logic to manage complex, multifactorial decision criteria significantly enhances the algorithm behind production scheduling. Practical applications of fuzzy logic in production scheduling emphasize its practical relevance across various industries. From manufacturing facilities to supply chain

management, the benefits of fuzzy logic extend beyond theoretical considerations, providing tangible improvements in operational efficiency and product quality.

Future perspectives include the development of a user interface for the presented system and the increase of its versatility by introducing new variables and providing the possibility of its adaptation to other applications in various industrial environments.

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